

C-Arm Guided Sacroiliac Joint Injection Techniques

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INTRODUCTION

Sacroiliac (SI) joint pain account for 16%-30% of axial low back pain. The pain is localized in the SI joint and can be replicated through provocation tests, and treatment consists multidisciplinary approach depending on the etiology. The condition can be reliably alleviated by using C-arm guided SI joint injection.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The primary target is the posterior inferior opening of SI joint just below the posterior inferior iliac spine (PSIS), with the needle trajectory following the angle of SI joint posterior opening. SI joint opens obliquely from the posteromedial to the anterolateral direction, and this opening angle differs for every patient.

Step 1: Patient in a prone position.

Step 2: C-arm comes in from the patient side in anteroposterior projection, tilted caudally and rotated contralaterally to get tunnel vision of the posterior SI joint opening.

Step 3: Needle infiltration aims just below the PSIS and beyond the posterior opening of SI joint.

Step 4: AP view is used to confirm the needle placement and depth.

Step 5: lateral view to ensure the needle does not pass anteriorly beyond the sacrum and not in the caudal direction to avoid visceral organ injury.

Step 6: Contrast solution should fill the joint space and spread laterally to the needle tip.

RESULTS

SI joint injection with local anesthesia and corticosteroid provides immediate pain relief for up to 1 year.

DISCUSSION

SI joint injection is a safe procedure with low reported complications such as infection, hematoma, sciatic nerve injury, particulate embolism, mild sciatica, temporary paresthesia, and weakness due to extravasation of injectate.

Therefore, this interventional pain management technique could be used for patients resistant to conservative pain therapy

Figure 1: C-arm position of A (AP), B (Caudal tilt), C (Contralateral tilt)

Figure 2A: Contralateral oblique view right SI joint with black arrow pointed to PSIS. Figure 2B: Lateral safe view shows, needle does not go beyond the anterior sacrum

CONCLUSION

The success rate depends on the expertise of the physician performing the procedure, understanding the patient's specific anatomy, and correct fluoroscopy techniques to guide the injection.

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